

Popular Article

Pythium insidiosum: Fungus - like organism of Veterinary importance

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Introduction

Pythium insidiosum, fungus - like organism is also known as *Hyphomyces destruens*. It is classified under the class *Oomycetes*, kingdom Chromista (Protista). It is found in aquatic environments and is an opportunistic animal pathogen whereas many other *Pythium* species are important as plant pathogens. Infection with *P. insidiosum* is rare in animals. Plant infections are essential for the propagation of the organism and the production of motile zoospores. *Pythium insidiosum* grows on a variety of laboratory media when incubated at both 25°C and 37°C. However, zoospores are produced only in water cultures. On solid media and in plant and animal tissues, the organism develops aseptate hyphae (4 to 10 µm in diameter) which are similar morphologically to those of the zygomycetes. Pythiosis, characterized by granulomatous lesions in subcutaneous or intestinal tissues, has been reported in horses, dogs, calves, sheep and cats. *Pythium insidiosum* is usually found in stagnant inland waters and occasionally in soil.

Pathogenicity:

Motile zoospores, which are apparently attracted by chemotaxis to wounds and abrasions on skin or intestinal mucosa, encyst on the exposed tissues. The encysted zoospores secrete a sticky material, possibly glycoprotein, which allows adhesion to tissues prior to invasion. Aseptate hyphae, which develop from germ tubes produced by the zoospores at body temperature, extend into the tissues and may invade blood vessels, facilitating dissemination and producing thrombosis. Infection evokes a cellular immune response consisting mostly of eosinophils. Much of the tissue damage arising from the infection is thought to result from degranulation of eosinophils and mast cells.

Clinical infections

Pythiosis is a rare, sporadic, non - contagious condition which occurs mainly in tropical and subtropical regions. Although horses and dogs are the species most commonly infected, a few cases have been reported in calves.

Pythiosis in horses

In horses, usually cutaneous pythiosis is observed, although intestinal pythiosis has also been reported. Lesions usually occur on those parts of the body, particularly the limbs, which come in contact with water containing zoospores. Lesions are large, circular, granulomatous nodules which often ulcerate. Sinus tracts may develop exuding a sero - sanguineous discharge. Pruritus is noticeable. Necrotic yellowish coral - like masses ('kunkers' or 'leeches') can be removed intact from the granulomas. In addition to necrotic tissue, these masses contain eosinophils and hyphae of *P. insidiosum*. Bone involvement can occur in chronic disease. Surgical excision of lesions followed by immunotherapy has proved successful in some cases. Enteric pythiosis is characterized by stenotic fibrous gastrointestinal lesions.

Pythiosis in dogs

Canine infection most commonly involves the stomach and small intestine. Subcutaneous pythiosis is less commonly encountered. Intestinal lesions are usually extensive when an affected animal is first presented for examination. Clinical signs include vomiting, weight loss, intermittent diarrhoea and palpable abdominal masses. Extension of the infection to the pancreas, mesenteric lymph nodes and bile ducts may occur. Cutaneous lesions, which occur on limbs, face or tail, are granulomatous nodules often with discharging sinus tracts. Surgical excision of lesions and long - term treatment with itraconazole may be beneficial.

Diagnostic Approaches

- The nature and distribution of lesions and a history of access to stagnant water in areas where pythiosis occurs may indicate the disease.
- Specimens, including biopsy material and samples from cutaneous lesions in horses, should be delivered immediately to the laboratory.
- Samples for transportation should be washed in sterile distilled water and transported at ambient temperature.
- Tissue sections, stained by the PAS or methenamine silver methods, are used to demonstrate hyphal forms.
- Immunofluorescence or immunoperoxidase techniques can be used to identify *P. insidiosum* in tissue sections.
- Detection and identification of *P. insidiosum* has been achieved using a nested PCR assay.

- Sabouraud dextrose agar, inoculated with material from lesions, is incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24 to 48 hours. The colonies, which are flat, whitish and radiating, may be up to 20 mm in diameter after 24 hours.
- Serological tests such as agar gel diffusion and ELISA have been used for the diagnosis of pythiosis in affected animals.